

ENZYMATIC ACTIVITIES OF LIVER ASSOCIATED WITH LOW, MODERATE AND HIGH INTENSITIES EXERCISE; A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

Dr. Alamgir Khan^{*1}, Dr. Muhammad Zafar Iqbal But², Shehzadi Sanam Roohi Farooqi³ Manzoor Khan⁴, Munir Khan⁵, Muhammad Saleem Akhtar⁶, Mir Jahanzeb Javeed⁷, Farooqi⁸, Muhammad Ahmad Raza⁹, Hassan Kamran¹⁰, Zeliha Selamoglu¹¹

^{*1,2,6}Department of Sports Sciences & Physical Education, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

²Department of Sports Sciences and Physical Education, Riphah international University Faisalabad Campus

^{3,4,8,9}Department of Sports Sciences & Physical Education, University of Science & Technology, KP, Pakistan.

⁵Harrisburg University of Science and Technology.

¹¹Department of Medical Biology, Medicine Faculty, Nigde Omer Halisdemir University, Nigde, Türkiye.

¹¹Department of Biology, Faculty of Sciences, Khoja Akhmet Yassawi International Kazakh-Turkish University, Turkestan, Kazakhstan.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17099659>

Keywords

Low intensity Exercise, Moderate Intensity Exercise, High Intensity Exercise, Enzymatic Activities, Liver

Article History

Received: 11 June 2025

Accepted: 21 August 2025

Published: 11 September 2025

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Alamgir Khan

Abstract

This study primarily aimed to assess the modulation of enzymatic activities associated with the low, moderate and high-intensity exercise. A systematic review following the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) declaration, and thus the key search engines, i.e. Web of Science, Science Direct, PubMed, Google Scholar and Scopus, were used for the collection of relevant literature. Likewise, studies carried out from 1st July 2018 to 1st July 2024 were included and assessed through the process of qualitative data analysis (QDA) technique. Fifty (50) research studies were retrieved from the key search engines, and finally twenty (2120) studies were evaluated by the application of the Physiotherapy Evidence Scale (PEDro). Based on the ethnicity of the results by following the criteria of PEDro, and thus the results show that low, moderate and high-intensity exercise have a significant impact on the basic liver enzymes, i.e. ALT, ALP and AST. The evidence also indicated that low and moderate-intensity exercise has a more significant impact on the enzymatic activities of the liver; hence, the various supplementations with high-intensity exercise lead to a healthier liver. Hence, no such type of study has been found, which indicates the comparison of various exercise intensities and frequencies with relation to the enzymatic activities of the liver. Based on the key findings of the study, a research study with a solid background needs to be conducted to examine the impact of various exercise intensities and frequencies with the context to enzymatic activities of the liver, with special context to athletes and non-athletes.

INTRODUCTION

The liver is one of the most important organs performing a variety of functions including detoxification of several metabolites, synthesizing proteins, and producing digestive enzymes (Lala,

Zubair, & Minter,2023) [16]. The liver is also known or considered a gland because it makes some chemicals needed by the body for performing different physiological activities such as metabolism,

regulation of red blood cells (RBCs), glucose synthesis and storage and cleansing toxins (Michalopoulos & Bhushan, 2021) [17]. Livers also play a vital role in activities and deactivation of anticancer agents-cytotoxics or new biological agents during metabolic activities of the body.

Structurally and functionally the liver is heterogeneous and complex helps in accomplishment of many functions for the organism particularly in regenerating after injury for the purpose to maintain the whole-body homeostasis and guarantee the survival of the individual (López & Fabregat Romero, 2018) [18].

Liver supply blood to both arteries and venous. The structural organization of liver to both arteries and venous supplier to mix and to bathe the various structures and cells in the liver with their contents. Oxygenated blood enters to liver through hepatic artery but this minor source of blood supplies to liver. The maximum blood enters to liver supplied by the portal vein. Portal blood rich in both nutrients and pathogen-derived molecules. For example, lipopolysaccharide (LPS) (Kubes, & Jenne, 2018) [19].

Human liver plays a vital role in metabolic activities of the body such as Carbohydrate metabolism: (regulates blood sugar levels), protein metabolism (breaks down proteins into amino acids), fat metabolism (processes fats for energy storage and utilization and hormone regulation (Produces and regulates hormones (e.g., insulin, thyroid). In addition, the liver also has detoxification functions including filtering toxins (removing harmful substances from blood), xenobiotic metabolism (breaking down drugs, chemicals, and pollutants and alcohol metabolism (Processing and eliminating alcohol). Along with these functions, some other functions of the liver are; bile production (produces bile to aid fat digestion, bilirubin processing, breaks down bilirubin from red blood cells and cholesterol regulation (produces and regulates cholesterol. The liver also stores glucose as glycogen, vitamin and mineral storage, stores vitamins A, D, E, K, and B12, and minerals like iron and copper and regulate blood volume (Lehrich & Monga, 2024) [21].

Objectives of the Study

1. To evaluate the previous literature to assess the effects of low, moderate and high-intensity exercise on liver enzymes.

Research Questions

1. What effect does low-intensity exercise have on liver enzymes?
2. What effect does moderate intensity exercise have on liver enzymes?
3. What effect does high intensity exercise have on liver enzymes?
4. What remedies are suggested by previous literature about enzymatic activities and exercise with different volumes and intensities?

METHODS

The below procedures were used to reach certain findings and conclusions.

Search strategy

This particular research study primarily aimed to assess the modulation of Enzymatic Activities Associated with the Exercise of High-Intensity Interval Training. A systematic review following the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) declaration and thus the key search engines i.e. Web of Science, Science Direct, PubMed, Google Scholar and Scopus was used for the collection of relevant literature. Exercise as the independent variable (IV) and enzymatic activities of the liver dependent variable (DV) were used for the collection of relevant data. Pilot screening was ensured for evaluating the title, abstract and keywords as well as the full-length article. For relevancy in terms of title and abstract of collected articles were evaluated by AK and MZ. Likewise, duplicate, as well as irreverent articles, were excluded during the pilot screening of the articles.

Eligibility criteria for the study selection.

The criteria for inclusion of studies were; Both Vivo and Vitro studies were included in the study, Studies carried out from 1st July 2018 to 1st July 2024, Studies available on Web of Science, Science Direct, PubMed, Google Scholar and Scopus data-based engines. While including articles demographic

attributes such as gender, and age were also taken into consideration. During the studies selection, the relevancy of the studies, specified time duration and specified search engines were also taken into account.

Data Extraction

Basic information about authors such as name, years of publications and country as well as details of an article such as randomizations of participants, anthropometric attributes of participants such as age, gender and BMI and details of exercise interventions (Volume, intensity, frequency). Likewise, pre and post-test results in terms of means, standard deviation and level of significance were recorded. The whole process of data extraction was completed by two authors of the study i.e. AK and MZ.

Study Quality

For making sure the methodological quality of articles, eligibility and bias risks, the Physical Therapy Evidence Database (PEDro) eleven-type scale was used and thus the finally twenty articles which fall in the excellent category were included.

RESULTS

Selection of Studies

During initial scrutiny only those studies carried out from 1st July 2020 to 1st July 2024 were included and assessed through the process of qualitative data analysis data (QDA) technique. one hundred and twenty (120) research studies were retrieved from the key search engines and finally twenty (15) studies were evaluated by the application of the Physiotherapy evidence scale (PEDro). The fig no.1 showing the PRISMA flow chart of inclusion and exclusion of articles in the study.

Fig no.1 Flow Chart of Studies Selection

Characteristics of Study Participants and Exercise Intervention

Basic information about authors such as name, years of publications and country as well as details of an article such as randomizations of participants, anthropometric attributes of participants such as age,

gender and BMI and details of exercise interventions (Volume, intensity, frequency). The detail of Characteristics of Study Participants and Exercise Intervention are given in below fig no.2

Author	Year	Participants	Exercise Intervention
Khan et al	2021	N=20 No sportsmen	Low intensity Exercise/ 12 weeks
Nath et al	2020	N=37, Police Trainees	Low/ Moderate Intensity Exercise/ 24 Weeks
Jamshidi et al	2024	N=80, Workers	Low intensity exercise/ 18 Weeks
Shakoor et al	2023	N=08, Rats	Moderate intensity Exercise/ weeks
Haxhi, et al	2024	N= 100 , Patients	Moderate to High Intensity/ 4 Weeks
Rengers et al	2021	N=28 Female	High intensity exercise/ 12 Weeks
Khan et al	2022	N=40 Male	High Intensity Exercise/ 12 weeks
Iraji, Minasian & Kelishadi	2021	N=23 Obese Male	High Intensity/ 8 Weeks
Nayebifar,, Ghasemi,& Karimipour,	2020	N=32 Young Men	High Intensity Exercise /8 weeks
Aliniya et al	2020	N=40 Obese Women	Moderate Intensity Exercise/ 12 weeks
Khaleghzadeh et al	2020	N=36 Adult Male	High Intensity Exercise/8 Weeks
Sargazi & Taghian	2020	N=80 HealthY Male	Low Intensity Exercise/ 8 Weeks
Atefi et al	2022	N=60 Healthy Women	Low Intensity/ Routine Life style/ Supplimentation
Lorestan et al	2020	N=24 /Children	Low intensity Exercise/ 12 weeks
Mascaró et al	2022	N=155 Health Adult	Low Intensity Exercise/Routine Activities

Low-intensity exercise and Liver Enzymes

Four (04) studies included with context to low intensity exercise was included. The RCT with 08 weeks of low intensity exercise with heathy male student’s athletes was conducted and found that low-intensity exercise has a significant impact on liver enzymes such as ALT and ALP. The level of ALT and ALP was found to be significantly higher (p<0.05) as compared to the control group (CG) (Khan et al, 2021) (1). Another study indicated that low-intensity exercise has a significant impact on the Alanine aminotransferase enzyme (p=0.001). (Jamshidi et al, 2024) (3). A result of quasi quasi-experimental study was carried out among 80 men and thus eight weeks of low-intensity exercise with royal jelly supplementation was applied to the

experimental group. The results of the study show that Eight weeks of royal jelly supplementation and resistance band exercise reduced serum levels of liver enzymes i.e ALT, ALP and AST (T4hroughout, P <0.05 was considered statistically significant.) in opium addicts undergoing MMT (Sargazi & Taghian, 2020)(12).

An RCT was conducted among 60 women with normal routine activities with sunflower oil (SFO) was conducted. The result of the study indicated a Significant reductions in body weight, body mass index (BMI), waist circumference (WC), and fatty liver grade were observed in both groups (P < 0.05). Following SO, significant decreases in serum aspartate and alanine aminotransferases (AST and ALT) were observed (P > 0.05) (Atefi et al,2022)

(13). A RCT shows that aerobic training with low intensity has a positive impact on body weight as well as enzymatic activities of the liver (liver enzymes ALT ($P = 0.002$), AST ($P = 0.003$), and ALP ($P = 0.047$), and anthropometric indices BMI ($P = 0.001$) and WC ($P = 0.043$) and increased the level of T3 ($P = 0.011$) in the experimental group (Lorestan et al, 2020) (14).

An experimental study was conducted by Khan et al (2019) for the assessment of low intensity exercise and its impact upon liver enzymes. Participants of the study were selected from Gomal University Dera Ismail Khan, Kp, Pakistan and thus the subjects were divided into two groups (Experimental Group and Control Group) through the application of International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ) and measurement of Maximum Heart Rate (MHR). 12 weeks self-made low intensity exercise protocol was applied to an experimental group. 5ml blood was collected from all subjects to measure the effect of low intensity exercise on ALT and ALP. The data of pre and post-test were processed through SPSS version 24. Based on analysis and findings, the researcher concluded that in experimental group (EXG) the level of ALT and ALP was found significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) as compared to control group (CG).

Moderate-intensity exercise and Liver Enzymes

Four (04) studies included with context to moderate intensity exercise was included. An experimental study with 37 police constables was conducted. The result of the study shows that moderate intensity caused a significant change in body mass index ($p = 0.001$), serum triglycerides, cholesterol ($p = 0.017$), serum transaminases ($p < 0.001$) and HOMA-IR ($p < 0.001$), and regression of ultrasonography fatty change in liver among NAFLD subjects (Nath et al, 2020) (2). The study found that moderate-intensity exercise has a significant impact on ALP at T8, T12 vs. T0 ($p < 0.01$), and increased HDL at T8 and ALT at T8 and T12 vs. T0 ($p < 0.05$) (Shakoor et al, 2023) (4). A Randomized control trial with 40 obese women was conducted and exercise with moderate intensity for 12 weeks was applied to the study participants the study found a significant change in serum level AL in the exercise + supplement group

($P = 0.00$), exercise group ($P = 0.00$), and supplement group ($P = 0.00$) was significantly reduced as well as the serum level of AST in the exercise + supplement group ($P = 0.00$), exercise group ($P = 0.000$), and supplement group ($P = 0.001$); and the serum level of ALP in the exercise + supplement group ($P = 0.01$), exercise group ($P = 0.002$), and supplement group ($P = 0.001$) (Aliniya et al, 2020) (11). A cross-sectional experimental study with 155 participants was conducted with moderate intensity exercise and found that NAFLD patients with high PA showed a more positive relationship on MetS parameters and liver profile (ALT, GGT, IFC-NMR) than subjects with low PA, but not for AST ($p < 0.001$) (Mascaró et al, 2022) (15).

High-Intensity Exercise and Liver Enzymes

Seven (07) studies included with context to high intensity exercise was included. The results of the study reveal that exercise with moderate to high intensity caused behaviour as well as beneficial effects on NAFLD markers in people with type 2 diabetes (Haxhi, et al, 2024) (5). Another study shows that High-intensity interval training has a significant impact on liver enzymes such as decreased was observed in ALP and AST (ALP, $P = 0.013$, AST, $P = 0.002$) (Rengers et al, 2021) (6).

A study was carried out among non-professional athletes and the result of the study indicated that high-intensity exercise without nutritional supplementation has a significant impact on liver enzymes (ALT ($t_{38} = -4.369$, $p < 0.05$), ALP ($t_{38} = -0.757$, $p > 0.05$), AST ($t_{38} = -2.246$, $p < 0.05$) and FRAP ($t_{38} = 4.308$, $p < 0.05$) (Khan et al, 2022) (7).

The study with 23 children and adolescents was randomly selected and thus high-intensity interval training was applied for eight weeks thus the study found a significant impact on liver enzymes such as AST, ALP and ALT ($P < 0.05$). A semi-experimental research study with 34 obese males was conducted with high-intensity exercise of eight weeks was applied on the study participants and thus ALT and AST were assessed as liver enzymes the result of the study shows that exercise with high intensity caused a reduction in the level of insulin resistance, triglyceride, total cholesterol, ALT, and AST in both groups, although high-density lipoprotein levels

decreased only in the HIIT group ($p < 0.01$). (Iraji Minasian & Kelishadi, 2021)(8). High-intensity exercise of 6 weeks with omega-3 supplementation had a significant impact on the liver enzymes (AST ($P = 0.01$), fat percentage ($P = 0.01$), while there was no significant difference in the TC, ALP, and WC levels ($P > 0.05$) (09). Exercise with high-intensity interval training caused a significant decrease in AST in plasma levels and a significant increase in VO_2 max. Besides, eight-week administration of supplementary Oligopin resulted in a significant decrease among male adults (Khaleghzadeh et al, 2020) (10).

CONCLUSION

After critical analysis of previous literature, the study concluded that low, moderate and high-intensity exercise has a significant impact on the basic liver enzymes i.e. ALT, ALP and AST. The evidence also indicated that low and moderate-intensity exercise having a significant impact on the enzymatic activities of the liver. The study also found that various supplementations with high-intensity exercise lead to healthier liver. Hence no such type of study found which indicates the comparison of various exercise intensities and frequencies with context to enzymatic activities of the liver. Based on the key findings of the study, a research study with a solid background needs to be conducted to examine the impact of various exercise intensities and frequencies with context to enzymatic activities of the liver with special context to athletes and non-athletes.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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